

LAKBAY-DIWA
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4397

p-ISSN 3082-5741

VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 4

ECHOES

of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

APRIL 2026
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

**Echoes of Expression
A Creative Folio**

Volume II, Issue IV (April 2026), National Circulation
ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741
Published Online at www.lakbay-diwapublishing.com
Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

GLENN PAULO K. LABASAN

Ifugao State University
Ifugao, Cordillera Administrative Region, Philippines
DOI 10.5281/zenodo.19856128

The Heart of a Medical Social Worker

It is a crowded place to be,
where time moves fast relentlessly.
Amid worried faces, fear and pain,
hope still rises, again and again.

There's always a line that never ends,
of people seeking help to mend.
With silent prayers and hearts unsure,
they come in faith, their strength secure.

As a medical social worker, I stand,
with duty and care, with heart and hand.
To assess with truth, with empathy,
to serve each life with dignity.

Each day I meet new stories told,
of fragile lives and courage bold.
A mother begging for her child's care,
a patient lost in deep despair.

A father strong, yet tears unseen,
hiding fears of what has been.
In every case, in all I do,
I listen, assess, and guide them through.

I bridge the gap, I find the way,
to help them face another day.
Though cases come in endless streams,
I stand with them through shattered dreams.

But there are days when limits show,
when help feels small against the woe.
Too many needs, too little time,
a heavy weight, a silent climb.

Still, I go home with stories deep,
of lives I carry, souls I keep.
The burden stays, yet I remain,
with colleagues sharing in the strain.

VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 4

ECHOES of EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

Echoes of Expression
A Creative Folio

Volume II, Issue IV (April 2026), National Circulation
ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741
Published Online at www.lakbay-diwapublishing.com
Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

I know my purpose, clear and true,
this path is what I'm called to do.
To serve, to care, to still believe,
that even small acts can relieve.

Each little win, each life made whole,
restores the strength within my soul.
A spark of hope, a brighter day,
reminds me why I chose this way.

This field has taught me to be strong,
to stand for right, to serve lifelong.
I am more than the role I play,
I am the stories that chose to stay.

And as I teach and share what's true,
their voices live in all I do.
For every life I helped somehow,
still walks with me, then and now.